

Study and Prevention of Caries in Type 1 Diabetes

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Abstract: The problem of diabetes mellitus is currently still relevant throughout the world. Over the past 50 years, this disease has reached a pandemic level. According to the information given by the World Health Organization in 2012, the number of patients with diabetes in the countries of the world is 280 million, of which 480,000 are children. 2010 only in Russia information will receive if so, this disease with 3 million 200 thousand the patient to the list received 97 % of them are sugary type 2 diabetes did.

Key words: diabetes , periodontal disease, caries

Relevance of the topic

It was estimated that 11.25% of those examined had type 2 diabetes in the 2009 Diabetes Risk Screening Questionnaire produced by the Volgograd Center for Medical Prevention [Sabanov V. I., Dyachenko T. S., Berdnik E. Yu. // Bulletin Roszdravnadzor. - 2012. - No. 2. - S. 49-53.]. Diabetes mellitus _ as a result saliva glands structural structure will change and this own in turn saliva separation and of saliva biochemical composition to breakdown take will come As a result, xerostomia and many caries, candidiasis, halitosis development reason will [Carda C., Mosquera-Lloreda N., Salam L., et al al . // Med . Oral . Patol . Oral. Cir . Bucal . - 2006. - Vol . 11 (4).- R. 309–314 .] Diabetes worldwide across health storage system branch for current problem being remains _ This children between early disability and high death level to increase main of reasons is counted . of the world mostly in countries to diabetes against struggle according to national programs acceptance done despite his _ spreading not only adults , but also children between too increased is going 1 17 13 5 Diabetes or to insulin that related diabetes known this illness children and in teenagers the most a lot is a common type of diabetes . Oral diabetes _ space to the situation significant effect does _ That's why for children dentists this of the disease mouth in the void cause release possible has been complications and to himself special features about they know necessary [Nirmala SVSG, Saikrishna D., 2016]. The world across in all age groups of diabetes prevalence was 2.8% in 2000 reached if and by 2030 come his increase in prevalence to 4.4% pending [World Health Organization, 2018]. Diabetes is the level of glucose in the blood chronic rise or with hyperglycemia to be described and insulin secretion disorder , as well as insulin dysfunction come coming out multifactorial is a disease . Sugary diabetes This is called a peaceful epidemic _ disease health storage of the organization main problem being and it is in the world all 9% of deaths does [NazirMA , AlGhamdiL , AlKadiM , AlBejanN , AlRashoudiL , AlHussanM ., 2018]. Diabetes is common in the population the most a lot occurring metabolic from diseases is one and common to health effect doer different approach _ to diseases and to complications

reason will be Chronic hyperglycemia, diabetes constant feature considered different _ organs and to tissues especially capillary blood to organs rich in vessels effect retinopathy , neuropathy, nephropathy and blood vein to diseases take forthcoming [JL Harding , ME Pavkov , DJ Magliano , JE Shaw , EW Gregg , 2019].

Research purpose : with type 1 diabetes hurt caries disease in children to meet study , treatment and preventive effectiveness increase _ Research tasks : with type 1 diabetes hurt in children dental diseases cause release possible has been different risk factors to determine and evaluation _ with type 1 diabetes hurt in children of caries to meet study _ with type 1 diabetes hurt in children dental clinical examinations take to go with type 1 diabetes hurt in children caries prevention get and efficiency evaluation _ Research object of Bukhara region endocrinology medicine in stationary conditions in the center with treated type 1 diabetes 131 patients _ patients choose received Check methods : clinical-dental , laboratory . Clinical examination methods main and additional : basic check methods objective and subjective data gathered . Subjective check information basically of the patient from himself bro his his parents bro from a relative disease to history belongs to has been anamnestic data received _ Objective examination while the patient external vision , face- jaw branch and mouth space out of sight sorry , the face is soft tissues and the jaws touch see also _ mouth space members instrumental inspection , such as percussion and that's it similar check methods we used 28 28 28 28 28 9 Laboratory check methods : of blood common analytical , biochemical analytical Research methods . general clinical, dental and statistical research methods was used . Research scientific novelty : with type 1 diabetes hurt in children dental diseases development risk factors identified ; with type 1 diabetes hurt in children of caries meeting studied ; with type 1 diabetes hurt in children caries prevention get and efficiency evaluated ; Research of the results scientific and practical Significance : Research scientific importance from that is that with type 1 diabetes hurt in children dental diseases is available has been in case for new promising opportunities open gives _ Research practical importance from that is obtained _ results based on type 1 diabetes to diabetes played in children main dental diseases cause emits risk factors was determined . That's it suitable in case endocrinologists , dentists , pediatricians , etc common practice to doctors teeth to caries when met treatment tactics determination , treatment acceptable method selection , in this category in patients dental diseases prevention efficiency quality to improve possibility giving measures , as well as type 1 diabetes played in children dental diseases is available has been in case them in management continuity principle save to stay based on Of these all of them complications and economic expenses to reduce , too this in the contingent ill of children hey quality to improve help gives _ Research the results done increase Sugary to diabetes played in children main dental diseases and basically caries prevention to get targeted preventive measure events and theirs result according to received scientific to the results based on From practical work received results of diagnosis accuracy and of acceleration increase , as well as type 1 diabetes played caries disease in children prevention to get help gives , this while the patient the children diagnosis and treatment for directly and indirectly expenses to reduce possibility to give conditions gives birth to this category in children tooth caries own in time treatment through this category in children row diseases prevention to get service does _

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